

Supplemental Information for:

The mechanism of promoting rhizosphere nutrient turnover for arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi attribute to recruited functional bacterial assembly

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Supplementary Figures

Figure S1. Map of sampling sites.

Figure S2. Comparison of node-level topological features in six groups. The closeness centrality (a, c), and degree (b, d) of bacterial communities are shown. Significant differences were determined by Wilcoxon tests ($\alpha = 0.05$).

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Figure S3. Manhattan diagram showing changes in bacterial abundances. The Manhattan diagrams show changes in bacterial abundances between non-mycorrhizal rhizosphere samples and mycorrhizal samples (a, b, c), and between mycorrhizal WT and AM fungi-inoculated *ljcbx* samples (d). CK is the control of AM fungi colonization, representing rhizosphere samples of wild type *L. japonicas* (Miyakojima MG20) without AM fungi inoculation. WT is the control of mutant *ljcbx*, indicating rhizosphere samples of wild-type *L. japonicas* (Gifu-129 background) inoculated with AM fungi. The solid triangle represents significantly enriched bacteria in the rhizosphere. The hollow triangle represents significantly depleted bacteria, and the dot represents bacteria with no significant change. The dotted lines refer to the q value ($-\log P$) of 0.05.

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Figure S4. The Mean Decrease Gini Index (a), mean proportion (b) and difference in mean proportion (c) in mycorrhizal wild-type and AM fungi-inoculated *ljcbx1* groups.

Figure S5. Chord diagram indicating associations of rhizosphere-enriched bacteria and functional eggNOG categories.

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Figure S6. Concentrations of NH₄⁺-N, NO₃⁻-N, AP, and AK in soil from non-mycorrhizal and mycorrhizal samples (a) and from mycorrhizal WT and AM fungi-inoculated *ljcbx* samples (b). Boxplots show the median with upper and lower quartiles and whiskers represent 1.5× interquartile range. Statistical differences were determined by two-sided t-tests (n = 24; n.s., not significant; *P < 0.05; **P < 0.01; ***P < 0.001).

Figure S7. Total N, P, and K contents in shoots of plants from non-mycorrhizal and mycorrhizal samples (a) and from mycorrhizal WT and AM fungi-inoculated *ljcbx* samples (b). Box plots show the median with upper and lower quartiles and whiskers represent 1.5 $\times$ interquartile range. Statistical differences were determined by two-sided t-tests ($n = 12$ and 18 , respectively; *** $P < 0.001$).

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Figure S8. Redundancy analysis. (a) RDA showing the correlation of mycorrhizal and non-mycorrhizal samples with NPK-associated parameters. (b) RDA showing the correlation between the nine genera enriched in the rhizospheres of mycorrhizal plants and NPK-associated parameters. (c) RDA showing the correlation of samples from mycorrhizal WT and AM fungi-inoculated *ljcbx* with NPK-associated parameters.

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Figure S9. Collection of rhizosphere bacteria and detection of their functions in nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium turnover. (a) Rhizosphere bacteria collection. (b) Functional detection of rhizosphere bacteria in N, P and K turnover.

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Supplementary Tables

Table S1. Primers for characterization of arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi.

Combination	Target	Sequence(5'-3')	Primer	Direction	Fragment size
AMV4.5NF-AMDGR	SSU	AAGCTCGTAGTTGAATTCG	AMV4.5NF	Forward	300 bp
		CCCAACTATCCCTATTAATCAT	AMDGR	Reverse	
AML1-AML2	SSU	ATCAACTTTCGATGGTAGGATAGA	AML1	Forward	800 bp
		GAACCCAAACACTTTGGTTTCC	AML2	Reverse	

SSU, small subunit rRNA gene.

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Table S2. The relative abundances of genes responsible for soil microbial N-cycling. Gm, Gi, and Gv are the abbreviation of *Glomus mosseae*, *G. intraradices*, and *G. versiforme*, respectively.

KO	gene name	function	CK1	CK2	CK3	Gm1	Gm2	Gm3	Gi1	Gi2	Gi3	Gv1	Gv2	Gv3	WT1	WT2	WT3	<i>ljcbx1</i>	<i>ljcbx2</i>	<i>ljcbx3</i>
K02591	nifK	N ₂ fixation	1383	2052	1584	2358	2683	2115	2681	2696	2586	2758	2342	2794	3671	3557	3656	3515	3257	2556
K04561	norB	Nitric oxide reduction	4166	5777	3030	6250	6220	5273	6497	6875	6132	7221	5699	7324	9547	10274	9795	9211	9242	7458
K10946	amoC	Ammonia oxidation	0	0	0	12	4	4	20	16	28	8	24	8	168	180	200	148	120	108
K10945	amoB	Ammonia oxidation	0	0	0	6	2	2	10	8	14	4	12	4	84	90	100	74	60	54
K10944	amoA	Ammonia oxidation	0	0	0	6	2	2	10	8	14	4	12	4	84	90	100	74	60	54
K04015	nrfD	Nitrite reduction to ammonia	2407	2305	2157	2643	2555	3181	2827	1856	2715	2949	2620	2789	2096	2116	1928	2379	2378	1568
K02568	napB	Nitrate reduction	1241	949	571	262	276	235	313	319	271	299	246	314	345	313	342	337	256	231
K02567	napA	Nitrate reduction	1537	1166	1147	1031	992	1042	899	1469	1379	1153	919	1020	995	949	805	1097	762	826
K02588	nifH	N ₂ fixation	1235	1803	1466	2125	2430	1907	2390	2401	2346	2483	2120	2513	3437	3282	3376	3229	3073	2425
K02586	nifD	N ₂ fixation	1426	2098	1624	2420	2763	2175	2798	2779	2634	2820	2436	2893	3721	3603	3699	3542	3275	2573
K00371	narH	Nitrate reduction	4747	4035	4066	2023	2373	2120	1941	2802	2608	2232	2217	2206	2909	2555	2370	2778	2275	2372
K00370	narG	Nitrate reduction	4752	4019	4137	2025	2444	2147	1948	2868	2640	2271	2255	2221	2871	2491	2332	2693	2212	2345
K02305	norC	Nitric oxide reduction	56	75	37	90	92	66	98	91	106	86	97	121	483	470	496	495	470	404

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K00531	anfG	N ₂ fixation	38	47	38	67	80	62	83	81	59	77	80	83	96	103	95	113	78	69
K03385	nrfA	Nitrite reduction to ammonia	1499	1273	688	796	594	645	934	831	792	686	683	867	1986	2119	2047	2057	1880	1474
K00368	nirK	Nitrite reduction	1790	2029	2967	3216	3552	3884	3629	2949	3540	3560	3767	3718	3529	3383	2969	3531	3342	2767
K00362	nirB	Nitrite reduction to ammonia	5851	6312	7296	5356	6695	5241	6469	7196	6026	6268	6286	7090	7805	7194	7134	7269	5980	5723
K00363	nirD	Nitrite reduction to ammonia	9853	12988	9535	15003	15814	13614	15969	18662	15462	17748	14771	17628	21587	22755	22082	19748	18836	16405

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Table S3. The relative abundances of genes responsible for soil microbial P-cycling. Gm, Gi, and Gv are the abbreviation of *Glomus mosseae*, *G. intraradices*, and *G. versiforme*, respectively.

KO	gene name	function	CK1	CK2	CK3	Gm1	Gm2	Gm3	Gi1	Gi2	Gi3	Gv1	Gv2	Gv3	WT1	WT2	WT3	<i>ljcbx</i> ₁	<i>ljcbx</i> ₂	<i>ljcbx</i> ₃
K01126	ugpQ	glycerophosphoryl diester phosphodiesterase	2670 3	3204 5	2729 9	3460 4	3686 2	3304 7	3519 1	3773 5	3486 0	3937 8	3308 2	3738 3	4214 2	4246 5	4161 7	3959 1	3749 8	3173 3
K00873	PK	pyruvate kinase	1781 0	2235 9	1858 9	2651 3	2781 5	2455 0	2735 9	2993 1	2660 8	2995 8	2557 7	2953 1	3539 5	3546 2	3459 8	3284 5	3164 6	2684 6
K09474	phoN	phosphatase (class A)	524	709	922	847	1043	810	869	1041	1053	1119	688	936	1549	1449	1578	1523	1321	1127
K00858	ppnK	NAD ⁺ kinase	1833 0	2282 5	1776 5	2525 5	2621 8	2343 8	2579 0	2839 4	2564 8	2870 7	2404 4	2797 5	3405 1	3413 3	3339 7	3160 0	3041 7	2573 5
K00117	gcd	quinoprotein glucose dehydrogenase	2041 9	2611 9	1434 8	2824 7	2792 1	2459 5	2894 1	3240 2	2747 3	3269 4	2539 2	3143 5	3901 9	4220 0	4013 4	3639 8	3584 1	2935 5
K02041	phnC	phosphonate transport system, ATP-binding component	2802	3437	5134	4586	5373	5156	5359	4798	5152	5330	5376	5705	6373	5363	5113	5712	5101	4351
K02040	pstS	phosphate transport system, periplasmic-binding component	2545 0	3230 7	2544 8	3631 7	3817 5	3339 2	3759 1	4239 8	3744 9	4154 7	3532 6	4165 4	4995 0	5017 8	4964 1	4578 0	4489 0	3829 4
K02043	phnF	C-P lyase subunit, GntR family transcriptional regulator, phosphonate transport system regulatory protein	1085	1292	1634	1591	1924	1540	1987	2064	1629	1700	1896	2026	2591	2014	2085	2089	1818	1656
K02042	phnE	phosphonate transport system, membrane	2756	3448	5288	4037	5216	3876	4944	5136	4400	4589	4952	5449	6847	5892	5899	6004	5013	4775

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		component																		
K06162	phnM	C-P lyase subunit, alpha-D-ribose 1-methylphosphate 5-triphosphate diphosphatase	2819	3305	3937	4605	5134	5120	5377	4712	4936	5106	5367	5551	5734	4982	4734	5172	4728	3743
K06163	phnJ	C-P lyase subunit, alpha-D-ribose 1-methylphosphate 5-phosphate C-P lyase	1124	1339	1673	1656	2004	1609	2071	2143	1690	1776	1979	2110	2710	2142	2202	2230	1924	1743
K06166	phnG	C-P lyase subunit, alpha-D-ribose 1-methylphosphate 5-triphosphate synthase	1118	1331	1667	1648	1991	1601	2052	2131	1681	1763	1969	2101	2700	2133	2191	2222	1920	1738
K06167	phnP	C-P lyase subunit, phosphoribosyl 1,2-cyclic phosphate phosphodiesterase	1244 9	1644 4	1189 5	2093 3	2132 5	1948 7	2135 4	2345 0	2084 6	2398 6	1959 3	2307 5	2705 4	2803 6	2711 0	2498 3	2392 0	1998 3
K06164	phnI	C-P lyase subunit, alpha-D-ribose 1-methylphosphate 5-triphosphate synthase	1126	1340	1673	1657	2006	1609	2071	2144	1691	1777	1984	2111	2687	2136	2196	2218	1916	1736
K06165	phnH	C-P lyase subunit, alpha-D-ribose 1-methylphosphate 5-triphosphate synthase	1126	1341	1673	1658	2007	1609	2073	2145	1692	1778	1985	2112	2710	2141	2204	2233	1924	1740
K01922	phoP	phosphopantothenticysteine	552	584	839	1274	1154	1249	1161	2110	1547	1467	1142	1223	1526	1576	1366	1839	1209	1243

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		synthetase																		
K01078	olpA	acid phosphatase	1541	2043	1081	2350	2312	2063	2369	2706	2343	2711	2174	2588	3366	3694	3575	3088	3084	2581
			2	4	4	4	1	2	2	6	0	3	8	1	9	7	4	6	9	2
K01077	phoA	alkaline phosphatase	4942	5817	6412	7472	8015	7752	7669	8019	7792	8407	6998	8085	8809	8748	7866	8479	7716	6786
K03787	surE	5'/3'-nucleotidase	8969	1052	9571	1018	1095	9102	1063	1255	1048	1136	9522	1167	1593	1510	1494	1520	1327	1191
				5		3	9		7	6	9	5		5	4	1	7	0	4	8
K03788	aphA	acid phosphatase (class B)	1216	738	482	10	12	14	8	9	10	7	10	10	2	1	2	1	0	5
K07048	opd	phosphotriesterase	2373	2210	2506	1817	2284	2097	2054	2374	1977	1985	2111	1946	1228	1096	1130	1160	1004	898
		C-P lyase subunit, alpha-D-ribose 1-methylphosphate 5-triphosphate synthase																		
K05781	phnK	C-P lyase subunit, alpha-D-ribose 1-methylphosphate 5-triphosphate synthase	1124	1339	1673	1657	2006	1609	2073	2144	1691	1777	1981	2111	2711	2144	2204	2234	1925	1747
K05780	phnL	C-P lyase subunit, alpha-D-ribose 1-methylphosphate 5-triphosphate synthase	960	1074	1540	1398	1729	1383	1747	1827	1428	1475	1741	1805	2387	1830	1865	1907	1682	1551
K05306	phnX	phosphonoacetaldehyde hydrolase	653	775	575	908	888	809	1125	1591	919	1082	898	1083	1628	1685	1540	1724	1213	1220
K00940	ndk	nucleoside-diphosphate kinase	1807	2254	1714	2483	2579	2302	2535	2780	2515	2830	2353	2752	3284	3346	3284	3091	2943	2484
			9	6	7	8	4	5	2	2	3	1	3	5	0	3	7	3	2	7
K01093	appA	4-phytase	9279	1137	6741	1215	1231	1083	1219	1410	1227	1433	1145	1359	1636	1771	1717	1467	1471	1235
				1		6	9	8	7	3	5	1	2	0	3	7	3	8	4	9
K01113	phoD	alkaline phosphatase	1333	1828	1488	2312	2389	2130	2318	2611	2346	2646	2194	2520	3036	3081	3007	2839	2708	2296
			7	7	2	8	8	7	7	4	3	7	7	2	4	0	7	0	3	7
K01139	spoT	GTP diphosphokinase / guanosine-3',5'-bis(diphosphate) 3'-diphosphatase	4200	3457	2774	933	1220	905	1180	1296	1150	1089	1135	1360	2042	1622	1505	1723	1431	1624
K05813	ugpB	Glycerol-3-phosphate	4070	4040	4498	4795	5277	5311	5446	4738	5072	5210	5457	5567	5641	5323	4997	5424	4875	4155

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K05816	ugpC	transporter subunit, periplasmic-binding component Glycerol-3-phosphate transporter subunit, ATP-binding component Glycerol-3-phosphate transporter subunit, membrane component Glycerol-3-phosphate transporter subunit	2827	2800	2643	2494	3071	2340	3093	3218	2868	2679	3207	3567	4128	3751	3577	3690	3044	3074
K05815	ugpE	transporter subunit, membrane component Glycerol-3-phosphate transporter subunit	3275	3039	3526	3436	3724	4122	3939	3288	3662	3813	3879	3882	3374	3080	2816	3362	3169	2566
K05814	ugpA	transporter subunit	3321	3126	3597	3527	3787	4220	4011	3356	3808	3860	3965	3967	3453	3166	2881	3435	3240	2621
K03430	phnW	2-aminoethylphosphonate-pyruvate transaminase C-P lyase subunit,	611	726	912	771	845	719	971	1131	812	828	782	1056	885	828	862	953	783	699
K09994	phnO	aminoalkylphosphonate N-acetyltransferase	13	9	4	1	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	0	1	1	2	1	5
K01524	ppx	exopolyphosphatase / guanosine-5'-triphosphate,3'-diphosphate pyrophosphatase	3884 7	4712 5	3619 3	4824 9	5229 0	4369 3	5083 6	5626 5	5002 0	5515 6	4818 0	5603 0	6680 0	6711 8	6662 8	6106 0	5781 3	4971 9
K00886	ppgK	polyphosphate glucokinase phosphate transport system, membrane component	4589	5905	4504	7579	8007	7128	7622	9190	7809	8807	7544	8042	1021 1	1071 6	1066 5	8794	8609	7933
K02038	pstA	transport system, membrane component	1847 9	2313 6	1794 7	2551 5	2655 9	2377 3	2613 1	2868 7	2581 0	2901 0	2413 2	2809 1	3367 9	3416 3	3342 5	3137 2	3033 4	2551 5

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K02039	phoU	phoR/phoB inhibitor protein phoU phosphate transport system, ATP-binding component	2262 1	2799 6	2170 8	3229 7	3353 4	3015 7	3250 7	3707 1	3324 1	3711 0	3071 8	3518 3	4236 4	4378 8	4280 2	3895 5	3718 4	3215 0
K02036	pstB	phosphate transport system, ATP-binding component	1999 0	2496 4	1996 3	2858 7	2960 3	2737 1	2942 0	3113 3	2894 1	3245 5	2715 6	3130 5	3628 5	3684 1	3581 8	3413 6	3304 7	2748 3
K02037	pstC	phosphate transport system, membrane component	1873 4	2341 9	1824 3	2597 9	2706 5	2424 4	2666 1	2924 8	2628 4	2952 0	2459 0	2858 1	3423 8	3478 2	3394 9	3187 9	3079 0	2593 8
K03306	pit	inorganic phosphate transporter C-P lyase subunit, ribose	1761 7	2155 8	1688 7	2397 9	2491 9	2264 2	2457 6	2714 5	2417 9	2725 2	2276 2	2634 2	3132 7	3179 2	3088 4	2896 3	2791 3	2377 8
K05774	phnN	1,5-bisphosphokinase	1082	1288	1633	1588	1921	1538	1983	2060	1625	1697	1890	2022	2598	2018	2086	2093	1823	1656
K02044	phnD		3949	5227	6545	6669	7490	6742	7627	7052	7271	7385	7551	8437	1113 5	9793	9559	1028 7	9351	8283
K01507	ppa	inorganic pyrophosphatase	3224 9	4178 0	3131 4	4914 9	5100 0	4520 2	5052 7	5408 4	4924 8	5583 8	4668 9	5458 6	6601 9	6753 4	6645 5	6151 5	5846 2	4925 6
K00937	ppk1	Polyphosphate kinase	1616 9	1990 3	1438 9	2063 5	2178 9	1838 2	2141 2	2427 9	2050 8	2362 6	1986 3	2343 1	2904 4	2965 5	2910 0	2639 3	2507 7	2200 1
K00951	relA	GTP pyrophosphokinase two-component system, OmpR family, phosphate regulon response regulator PhoB	1781 1	2237 3	1732 2	2399 1	2537 0	2212 8	2461 2	2597 9	2404 3	2742 9	2288 9	2690 7	3174 1	3246 4	3218 3	2941 2	2849 9	2399 7
K07657	phoB	two-component system, OmpR family, phosphate regulon response regulator PhoB	1531 8	1870 4	1296 7	1919 5	1984 6	1691 5	1970 5	2228 1	1873 6	2183 2	1795 9	2146 6	2756 7	2828 8	2767 8	2501 0	2415 9	2063 7
K07636	phoR	two-component system, OmpR family, phosphate regulon sensor histidine	1886 5	2332 5	1773 4	2657 5	2709 2	2511 4	2743 1	2852 2	2668 4	3025 0	2497 1	2969 8	3468 0	3541 0	3441 7	3286 3	3155 0	2619 8

